

Search Ripples in Housing Markets: Quality, Location, and the Housing Cycle

Mari O. Mamre^a, Bjørnar Karlsen Kivedal^b

^a*Oslo Metropolitan University and Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway*

^b*Oslo Metropolitan University and Østfold University College, Norway*

Abstract

This article investigates housing-market search intensity as a measure of within-city market tightness. We use novel transaction-level auction data that distinguish two stages of observed search participation, registered interest and bidding. In line with a stylized model of segmented housing search, we find that search intensity varies systematically across quality tiers. During boom periods, search intensity is relatively higher for lower-quality dwellings. During bust periods, this gradient weakens and partly reverses toward higher-quality dwellings. Asking prices are more strongly negatively associated with bidding than with registered interest, consistent with bidding representing a later stage of participation. Quality-specific search intensity is also associated with price growth in the expected direction, and dynamic analyses suggest that changes in search intensity tend to precede changes in prices. These findings point to search intensity as an early indicator of market tightness and as a margin through which housing cycles may propagate across quality and location segments.

Keywords: Housing market search, housing quality, market tightness, house price ripples, auction participation

JEL: O18, D10, D83, R21

1. Introduction

In frictional and segmented housing markets, market outcomes depend not only on the aggregate number of buyers and sellers, but also on how market tightness is distributed across dwellings. Demand pressure may be concentrated in particular locations, price ranges, or dwelling types before it is fully reflected in transaction prices. Yet this distribution of buyer participation is difficult to observe directly. Most empirical studies therefore infer demand pressure from realized outcomes such as transaction prices, sales, or time on market.

Email addresses: corresponding author: mari.mamre@oslomet.no (Mari O. Mamre), bjornar.k.kivedal@hiiof.no (Bjørnar Karlsen Kivedal)

We appreciate valuable comments and suggestions from Harald Goldstein, Fateh Belaïd, Dag Einar Sommervoll, Paul Carrillo, Zeno Adams, André Anundsen, Frikk Nesje, Espen Moen, Endre Jo Reite, Brano Glumac and Erlend Eide Bø, as well as participants at Western Economics Association International (WEAI) 2024 in Washington, several research seminars and anonymous referees.

Recent work using online traffic and browsing behavior has made important progress in measuring housing search directly (Piazzesi et al., 2020; Gargano et al., 2023; Badar-inza et al., 2024). These measures provide valuable evidence on early-stage screening and consideration-set formation. Less is known about later-stage participation in specific dwellings, when potential buyers visit open houses, register interest, or enter bidding. Using transaction-level auction data, this article investigates housing-market search intensity as a measure of within-city market tightness. We observe registered interest and bidding at the listing level, close to price formation, and study how this late-stage search intensity varies across quality and location segments over the housing cycle. To our knowledge, the paper is among the first to use housing-auction participation data for this purpose.

To motivate the empirical analysis, we develop a stylized model of segmented housing search, based on Williams (2018). In the model, buyers allocate participation across quality segments, sellers post asking prices, and transaction prices are determined through bidder competition. The model delivers three implications that guide the empirical analysis. First, search intensity may vary across quality segments as market conditions change. Second, the transition from registered interest to bidding may be more sensitive to asking prices and affordability constraints. Third, because search participation is observed before final transaction prices are realized, it may contain information about later price dynamics.

The paper combines three margins of evidence. The core analysis estimates quality-by-phase interaction models to study how listing-level search intensity varies across quality tiers, locations, and market phases. A staged-search analysis then examines whether the pricing variables matter differently for registered interest and bidding. Finally, a time-series analysis studies whether quality-specific search intensity is associated with later price movements and propagation across segments. These latter analyses are used as supporting evidence and validation rather than as stand-alone causal designs.

We use transaction-level auction data from Norwegian urban housing markets. The data combine dwelling characteristics, prices, valuations, location measures, listing information, and auction participation. Registered interest is recorded directly in the auction data, while the number of bidders is constructed from minute-by-minute bidding logs. The main analysis focuses on Oslo, the largest metropolitan market, where the data allow us to study search participation across both quality and location segments. Additional urban markets are used to assess whether the main patterns are specific to Oslo. The Norwegian setting is well suited for studying late-stage search participation because high homeowner-ship rates and auction-based transactions make buyer participation observable for a broad segment of the market.

The findings are likely to be relevant beyond auction-based housing markets, although the strength and form of the mechanism may differ across institutional settings. In Norway, search intensity translates directly into bidder competition through ascending-bid auctions. In negotiated-sale markets, similar pressure may operate through sellers' bargaining power rather than formal bidding (Harding et al., 2003; Hayunga and Munneke, 2021; Krainer, 2001; Piazzesi and Schneider, 2009).

As the previous literature demonstrates, there is no universally accepted concept of

quality. In this study, we define housing quality tiers based on size, age, and a measure of the renovation status of the house at the time of sale described in [Mamre and Sommervoll \(2022\)](#). While necessarily incomplete, this definition captures key observable dimensions of the dwelling-quality bundle that are likely to be salient to buyers and allows us to study how search intensity varies across quality tiers, market phases, and locations.

The main finding is that search intensity is systematically distributed across housing quality tiers over the cycle. During boom periods, and after accounting for changes in listing composition, search intensity is relatively higher for lower-quality dwellings. During bust periods, this gradient weakens and partly reverses toward higher-quality dwellings. In the main Oslo specification, low-quality dwellings receive substantially more registered interest than medium-quality dwellings during booms, on the order of 15–20 percent, while the gap relative to high-quality dwellings is larger, around 25–30 percent. During busts, these differentials narrow substantially and the low-versus-high differential largely disappears. The pattern is similar when using bidders as the search measure and is robust across alternative specifications, spatial controls, and a size-based quality definition.

The phase-based estimates should be interpreted as average differences across price-cycle regimes. A semi-parametric spline specification yields a similar broad pattern, but shows that the quality gradient in search is not mechanically tied to price-cycle turning points. This is consistent with search intensity capturing a broader market-tightness margin than contemporaneous price growth alone.

The mechanisms behind these quality gradients are likely to be multiple. One interpretation, consistent with segmented-search models, is that stronger competition in preferred segments reduces the relative return to participation there and generates spillovers toward secondary or less preferred segments ([Williams, 2018](#)). Similar patterns may also reflect changes in financial constraints, collateral effects, speculative demand, clientele shifts, or transaction-timing mechanisms. The empirical analysis does not separately identify these channels, but documents their common implication. Market pressure, measured through search intensity, is redistributed across quality tiers over the housing cycle.

The supporting analyses are consistent with this interpretation. In the reduced-form staged-search analysis, asking price is negatively associated with both registered interest and bidding, but more strongly with bidding. Moreover, a stacked same-listing specification suggests that pricing relative to underlying value affects listing-specific attention broadly, while the overall asking-price level is more consequential for the transition into bidding.

The time-series evidence also generally points in the same direction. Quality-specific search intensity is associated with price growth in the expected direction. Moreover, vector autoregressions, Granger-causality tests, and local projections suggest that changes in search intensity often precede changes in transaction prices across quality and location segments. The fairly short time series means that this evidence is exploratory, but it supports the interpretation of registered interest as an early indicator of market pressure.

Taken together, the results imply that demand pressure within cities is not only spatially distributed, but also sorted across the quality distribution of the housing stock. Since urban housing markets are characterized by spatial patterning of housing qualities

and price levels (e.g., [Piazzesi and Schneider, 2009](#)), search intensity may serve as an early indicator of demand pressure and as a mechanism through which housing cycles spread across quality and location segments.

The empirical analysis has limitations. Most importantly, we do not observe the same buyer across multiple auctions and therefore cannot distinguish individual search reallocation from changes in the composition of market participants. Asking price also has a dual role. Conditioning on it provides within-price quality gradients, but asking price may itself direct search. We therefore report both price-controlled and no-price specifications and interpret the estimates as reduced-form associations. Future work linking individual search histories, financial constraints, and transaction outcomes would allow a more direct analysis of how households adjust search across quality and location segments over the cycle.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. [Section 2](#) reviews related literature. [Section 3](#) presents the stylized model. [Section 4](#) describes the data, quality classification, and spatial and temporal aggregation. [Section 5](#) presents the main search-intensity results, including heterogeneity across urban markets and Oslo submarkets. [Section 6](#) reports robustness checks. [Section 7](#) examines supporting mechanisms and validation evidence, including staged search, hedonic price growth, and dynamic search-price linkages. [Section 8](#) concludes.

2. Related Literature: Housing Search, Quality Segmentation, and Ripple Effects

This paper relates to three strands of housing-market research, covering search frictions and market tightness, segmentation by housing quality, and ripple effects across urban submarkets. Across these literatures, a common theme is that housing-market pressure need not be distributed uniformly across the housing stock. What remains difficult to observe empirically is how buyer participation is allocated across dwellings and submarkets before prices fully adjust.

A first strand studies search frictions, market tightness, and the housing-market matching process. Search-and-matching models emphasize how congestion, inventory, and trading frictions affect liquidity, turnover, and prices ([Wheaton, 1990](#); [Carrillo, 2012](#); [Ngai and Tenreyro, 2014](#); [Han and Strange, 2015](#)). Recent work has made progress by observing search behavior directly. [Piazzesi et al. \(2020\)](#) show that search is segmented across locations and housing characteristics, and that clientele patterns shape the response of housing markets to shocks. [Gargano et al. \(2023\)](#) show that local price growth expands the breadth of search across geography and dwelling characteristics, with spillover effects on prices and inventories. [Badarinza et al. \(2024\)](#) further show that matching outcomes depend on more than aggregate market tightness alone, including pricing strategy and intermediate stages of the matching process.

This paper complements that literature by studying a later stage of search participation. Online measures provide important evidence on how buyers form consideration sets, but they are less directly connected to transaction-stage participation and price formation.

We observe dwelling-level participation through registered interest and bidding. These measures capture engagement with specific dwellings after buyers have moved beyond online screening and are closer to match formation than browsing, clicks, or saved listings. This makes it possible to study within-city market tightness at the level of individual dwellings rather than through aggregate search breadth. The distinction between registered interest and bidding also connects the paper to work on the directing role of asking prices. [Han and Strange \(2016\)](#) show that asking prices direct buyer search even when they are neither binding commitments nor price ceilings. In our setting, asking price is examined as a potential pricing channel that may matter differently at different stages of participation.

A second strand studies segmentation by housing quality. Classical contributions view housing as a set of differentiated substitute goods organized in quality hierarchies or inter-related submarkets ([Sweeney, 1974a,b](#); [Cubbin, 1974](#); [Leishman, 2001](#)). In modern models, changes in income, wealth, credit conditions, or buyer composition generate filtering, re-sorting, and heterogeneous housing-cycle dynamics across segments ([Ho et al., 2008](#); [Ortalo-Magne and Rady, 2006](#); [Landvoigt et al., 2015](#); [Anenberg and Bayer, 2020](#)). This literature implies that booms and busts need not affect all parts of the housing stock symmetrically. Empirically, however, heterogeneity across quality segments has usually been traced through prices, turnover, inventories, or stock composition rather than through observed buyer participation. Our contribution is to bring a search-based measure to this literature. Using a composite quality proxy based on salient dwelling attributes, we study how demand pressure is distributed across quality tiers over the cycle rather than inferring that distribution only from realized prices or transactions.

A third strand examines ripple effects across space and market segments. Existing work studies whether shocks to house prices, credit conditions, or local demand propagate across regions, neighborhoods, or urban submarkets (e.g., [Meen, 1999](#); [Gupta and Miller, 2012](#); [Bogin et al., 2019](#); [Zhu et al., 2022](#)). A related literature also shows that market tightness and transaction timing can amplify housing-market cycles ([Moen et al., 2021](#)). This paper extends the ripple perspective from prices and locations to search intensity across the quality distribution. Since dwellings are bundles of location and structural quality, market pressure may propagate not only across neighborhoods, but also across quality tiers within the same city. [Appendix E](#) summarizes related studies that analyze cross-sectional differences in housing-market outcomes.

3. A Stylized Model of Segmented Housing Search with Asking Prices and Market Outcomes

To motivate the empirical analysis and explore relevant mechanisms, this section presents a stylized equilibrium model of segmented housing search with asking prices and auction-based transaction prices. The model builds on [Williams \(2018\)](#), but is tailored to the empirical setting of this study. Its purpose is not to model the full search process. Instead, it provides a simple framework linking search participation, listing composition, bidder competition, and final transaction prices across quality segments.

We adapt the framework in several ways. For simplicity, the market is represented

by two discrete quality segments. Sellers post asking prices while final transaction prices are determined through ascending-bid auctions. In addition, search intensity is defined as later-stage participation. Derivations are given in [Appendix A](#).

3.1. Environment

There are two housing-market segments indexed by $j \in \{H, L\}$, representing high- and low-quality dwellings. Segments may differ along several dimensions, including size, price, location, and dwelling quality. A continuum of buyers of mass B considers participating in the market, and sellers supply a flow of listings S_j in each segment.

Buyers choose segment-specific participation intensities $i_H, i_L \geq 0$ at cost

$$C(i_H, i_L) = \frac{\kappa}{2}(i_H + i_L)^2, \quad \kappa > 0.$$

The cost function captures costly effort devoted to actively engaging with listings in each segment.

3.2. Valuations, Registered Interest, and Bidders

Upon observing a listing in segment j , buyers draw a private valuation $v_j \sim F_j(v)$, where F_j follows a Pareto distribution with lower bound \bar{v}_j and shape parameter $\alpha_j > 1$, and where $\bar{v}_H > \bar{v}_L$. Each listing is posted with an ask price a_j and buyers observe this before deciding whether to register interest. A buyer registers interest in a listing if $v_j \geq a_j$. The probability of registering interest is $\iota_j(a_j) = 1 - F_j(a_j)$. The expected number of registered interested buyers per listing is

$$I_j = \frac{B \cdot i_j \cdot \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j}. \quad (3.1)$$

Among registered interested buyers, a subset enters the auction stage. Let

$$N_j = \phi_j(a_j)I_j, \quad 0 < \phi_j(a_j) \leq 1, \quad \phi_j'(a_j) \leq 0,$$

denote the expected number of bidders per listing, where $\phi_j(a_j)$ captures the conversion from registered interest to bidding, a potentially more affordability-constrained stage of search.

3.3. Auction Price Formation

Dwellings are sold through ascending-bid auctions. Under standard assumptions, the final transaction price is determined by the upper order statistics of bidder valuations and is therefore increasing in the number of bidders (see, for instance, [Milgrom and Weber \(1982\)](#) and [Klemperer \(1999\)](#)). We represent this relationship in reduced form as

$$p_j = P_j(N_j; \bar{v}_j, \alpha_j, a_j), \quad \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial N_j} > 0.$$

Thus, asking prices affect initial participation and the conversion from interest to bidding, while final transaction prices are determined endogenously through bidder competition.

3.4. Buyers' Problem

Buyers are atomistic and take asking prices, bidder competition, and expected transaction prices as given. Let $\pi_j(N_j) \in (0, 1]$ denote the probability of winning conditional on entering the auction, where

$$\pi'_j(N_j) < 0.$$

Let $\Delta_j(p_j)$ denote expected match surplus conditional on winning at price p_j . Under the Pareto assumption,

$$\Delta_j(p_j) = \frac{p_j}{\alpha_j - 1},$$

as shown in [Appendix A](#). This expression should be interpreted as a reduced-form term implied by the Pareto valuation distribution. It reflects the expected surplus among buyers whose valuations are sufficiently high to win at price p_j , rather than a direct positive effect of higher prices on buyer utility. For an individual buyer, R_j denotes the expected marginal gross return from one unit of search participation in segment j :

$$R_j = \iota_j(a_j)\phi_j(a_j)\pi_j(N_j)\Delta_j(p_j).$$

Thus, the net return to participation depends on two opposing forces. Higher expected transaction prices are associated with higher conditional valuations among successful buyers, captured by $\Delta_j(p_j)$, while greater bidder competition lowers the probability of winning, captured by $\pi_j(N_j)$.¹ Buyers choose participation intensities i_H and i_L to maximize expected surplus:

$$\max_{i_H, i_L \geq 0} \sum_{j \in \{H, L\}} i_j R_j - \frac{\kappa}{2} (i_H + i_L)^2.$$

For an interior solution, the first-order conditions are

$$\iota_j(a_j)\phi_j(a_j)\pi_j(N_j)\Delta_j(p_j) = \kappa(i_H + i_L), \quad j \in \{H, L\}. \quad (3.2)$$

Thus, search participation is allocated such that the marginal return is equalized across segments.

3.5. Partial Equilibrium

Given posted asking prices $\{a_j\}_{j \in \{H, L\}}$ and listing flows $\{S_j\}_{j \in \{H, L\}}$, a short-run equilibrium consists of segment-specific participation intensities, registered interest, bidders, and transaction prices,

$$\{i_j, I_j, N_j, p_j\}_{j \in \{H, L\}},$$

¹The relevant object for participation is therefore the product $\pi_j(N_j)\Delta_j(p_j)$, not $\Delta_j(p_j)$ alone.

such that the following conditions hold for each segment $j \in \{H, L\}$:

$$\iota_j(a_j)\phi_j(a_j)\pi_j(N_j)\Delta_j(p_j) = \kappa(i_H + i_L), \quad (3.3)$$

$$I_j = \frac{B \cdot i_j \cdot \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$N_j = \phi_j(a_j)I_j, \quad (3.5)$$

$$p_j = P_j(N_j; \bar{v}_j, \alpha_j, a_j). \quad (3.6)$$

Equations (3.3)–(3.6) jointly determine participation intensity, registered interest per listing, bidders per listing, and final transaction prices, conditional on posted asking prices and listing flows. The equilibrium is sequential and simultaneous in that participation determines registered interest per listing, registered interest maps into bidder competition, bidder competition determines final transaction prices, and expected competition and transaction prices feed back into the return to participation.

3.6. Comparative Statics

We consider two shocks: a buyer-demand shock and a listing-composition shock.

A. Buyer-Demand Shock ($B \uparrow$)

Consider first an increase in the mass of buyers, B . From equation (3.4), holding participation intensity fixed, registered interest per listing responds as

$$\frac{\partial I_j}{\partial B} = \frac{i_j \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j} > 0.$$

From equation (3.5), this increases the expected number of bidders per listing:

$$\frac{\partial N_j}{\partial B} = \phi_j(a_j) \frac{\partial I_j}{\partial B} > 0.$$

Finally, since final transaction prices are increasing in bidders per listing by equation (3.6),

$$\frac{\partial p_j}{\partial B} = \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial N_j} \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial B} > 0.$$

If bidder competition has a sufficiently stronger marginal effect on final transaction prices in the high-quality segment, then the initial price response to a buyer-demand shock is larger in that segment:

$$\frac{\partial p_H}{\partial B} > \frac{\partial p_L}{\partial B}.$$

The effect of higher demand on participation incentives depends on the net return $\pi_j(N_j)\Delta_j(p_j)$. Stronger demand increases bidder competition and final transaction prices. Higher transaction prices are associated with higher conditional valuations among successful buyers, captured by $\Delta_j(p_j)$, but greater competition also lowers the probability of winning, captured by $\pi_j(N_j)$. If the congestion effect dominates in the high-quality segment, the net return to participation may rise less, or fall more, than in the low-quality segment. This provides a mechanism through which aggregate search intensity may be

relatively higher for lower-quality dwellings during booms.

B. Listing-Composition Shock ($S_j \uparrow$)

Consider also an increase in the number of listings in segment j . From equation (3.4), holding participation intensity fixed, registered interest per listing responds as

$$\frac{\partial I_j}{\partial S_j} = -\frac{Bi_j l_j(a_j)}{S_j^2} < 0.$$

Thus, for a given mass of buyers and participation intensity, an increase in listings mechanically reduces measured search intensity per listing. From equation (3.5), the expected number of bidders per listing also falls:

$$\frac{\partial N_j}{\partial S_j} = \phi_j(a_j) \frac{\partial I_j}{\partial S_j} < 0.$$

Finally, since final transaction prices are increasing in bidder competition by equation (3.6),

$$\frac{\partial p_j}{\partial S_j} = \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial N_j} \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial S_j} < 0.$$

Changes in listing composition therefore affect measured market tightness and final transaction prices directly, even in the absence of a buyer-demand shock. Thus, listing composition is a separate channel through which search intensity may vary across housing segments.

3.7. Empirical Implications

The model and institutional setting yield three empirical implications: (i) Search intensity may vary across quality segments as market conditions change. (ii) The transition from registered interest to bidding may be more sensitive to asking prices and affordability constraints. (iii) Search intensity may contain information about later price dynamics.

The first implication follows from two channels. Stronger competition in preferred segments can reduce the relative return to participation in those segments and provide a mechanism through which aggregate search intensity is relatively higher for lower-quality dwellings during booms. At the same time, changes in listing composition affect measured market tightness directly by changing the number of searchers per listing. Empirical comparisons across quality tiers should therefore account for changes in the observable composition of listed dwellings over the cycle. The comparative statics should be interpreted as short-run and partial-equilibrium results.

Guided by these implications, the empirical analysis proceeds in three steps. The first and main step estimates how later-stage search intensity varies across quality tiers over the cycle, using both boom–bust indicators and a more flexible time specification, while adjusting for phase-specific differences in listing composition. The theoretical model uses two quality segments to capture the basic mechanism, whereas the empirical analysis uses three quality tiers to estimate gradients in the data.

The second step examines supporting mechanisms by testing whether asking price is differently associated with registered interest and bidding, consistent with the staged-search interpretation. The third step studies whether search intensity contains information about later market outcomes through the joint dynamics of search intensity and final transaction prices, using lead-lag evidence, vector autoregression (VAR) models, and Granger-causality tests.

4. Data Description: Search Intensity, Quality, and Temporal Segmentation

Figure 1: Timeline of Search in the Housing Market

Notes: The figure illustrates the sequence of observed and unobserved search stages in the housing market. The data used in this paper observe later-stage participation through registered interest and bidding, but do not observe individual online screening.

The analysis employs a cross-sectional dataset of housing transactions in four Norwegian cities, sourced from Eiendomsverdi ASA and coupled with the house-listing text from the main real estate portal Finn.no. The transaction data are further matched to auction information obtained from five large broker organizations operating in the study areas. The auction data contain two measures of observed search participation. The first is registered interest, recorded directly in the auction data. The second is the number of bidders, which we constructed from minute-by-minute bidding logs by aggregating unique bidder identifiers within each auction. In the main analysis, we use data for the metropolitan market, Oslo, starting from 11,683 sales. This sample is reduced to 8,470 transactions after excluding observations that lack information on the auction, asking price, or other key variables. Missing variables are handled through listwise deletion, resulting in limited data loss. Comparable data operations are performed for the other urban areas, with summary statistics reported in the Online Appendix.

To register interest or place a bid, potential buyers must contact the broker at the auction, by email, or by telephone. The two measures therefore differ in the degree of purchase commitment. The first captures listing-specific participation before the auction stage, while bidding captures active participation in price formation. We also observe the number of bids in each auction, which depends on both the number of bidders and their bidding strategies. We therefore treat the number of bids as an auction outcome rather than as a direct measure of search intensity. In addition, the data include a proxy for time on market (TOM) and final transaction prices. On average, transacted dwellings in the Oslo sample had 16.7 registered interested buyers, 3 bidders, received 9.6 bids, spent 58 days on the market, and were sold for about USD 418,500.

A potential limitation is that registered interest may partly reflect seller- or broker-side effort, since agents and sellers differ in networks, marketing routines, and marketing intensity. We do not observe individual broker fixed effects or marketing regime, and therefore control for real estate agency. The measure remains informative because it is observed close to the auction stage, where matching probabilities, bidder competition, and price formation are determined.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
<i>Search and auction outcomes</i>					
Registered interest	16.73	13.0	14.8	1	166
Bidders	2.98	2.0	2.1	1	20
Bids	9.61	8.0	7.3	1	72
Time on market ^a	58.36	35.0	77.3	0	1,959
<i>Prices and dwelling characteristics</i>					
Transaction price	418.5	355.6	208.1	101.4	3,057.4
Ask price	400.4	338.7	208.2	94.3	4,233.3
Size ^b (m ²)	72.96	65.0	40.3	14	503
Dwelling age	57.31	58.0	37.6	0	188
Distance to CBD, km	3.92	3.19	2.3	0.27	12.3
<i>Quality indicators</i>					
Fully renovated	0.068	–	–	0	1
Unmaintained	0.084	–	–	0	1
Newly developed ^c	0.055	–	–	0	1

Notes: The table reports summary statistics for the main Oslo sample. $N = 8,470$. The sample period is July 2013–June 2019. Prices are reported in USD 1,000 using an exchange rate of 10.63 NOK/USD. Distance to CBD is the Haversine distance to Oslo Central Station. Binary quality indicators are reported as sample shares.

^aTime on market is measured as the number of days from the realtor received the assignment until the dwelling was sold. ^bSize is measured as the area of primary rooms. ^cNewly developed dwellings are three years old or less.

4.1. Quality Segmentation

For tractability, each transacted dwelling is classified into one of three quality tiers, $Q \in \{low, medium, high\}$. The classification is based on observable characteristics likely to be salient to buyers at the time of search, including size, newness, and renovation status. Size captures an important and largely fixed dimension of dwelling quality, while renovation status and newness capture more flexible aspects of the housing bundle. A dwelling can be renovated over time, but its size and location are more difficult to adjust.

High-quality units are defined as dwellings that satisfy at least one of the following criteria. They belong to the top 15 percent of the size distribution, or they are fully renovated at the time of sale, as indicated in the listing², or they are newly built, defined as three years since construction or less. Low-quality units are defined as dwellings that belong to the bottom 15 percent of the size distribution, or are unmaintained at sale.³ The

²See Mamre and Sommervoll (2022) for details on the renovation criteria.

³In the capital Oslo, the housing stock contains a relatively large share of small units. As an exception, the bottom 20 percent is classified as low quality in that market, corresponding to a size threshold of approximately 50 square meters across cities.

Figure 2: Classification of housing quality tiers

Notes: The figure illustrates the rule-based classification of dwellings into mutually exclusive quality tiers. Dwellings satisfying the high-quality rule are classified first. Among the remaining dwellings, those satisfying the low-quality rule are classified as low quality. All other dwellings are classified as medium quality.

remaining dwellings are classified as medium quality. The three categories are mutually exclusive, and the decision-tree classification is shown in Figure 2. Several alternative classification schemes could be constructed from these characteristics. In the robustness analysis, we test sensitivity to an alternative size-only definition of quality. Figure 3 provides descriptive evidence on search intensity by quality tier across the four urban markets showing that search intensity for the low-quality segment tends to rise during periods of stronger house price growth.

4.2. Spatial and Temporal Aggregation

The analysis uses two definitions of spatial aggregation: *price zones* and conventional *administrative areas*. Price zones are spatially non-contiguous groups of areas with similar estimated location premiums. They are constructed using the machine-learning classification procedure developed in [Sommervoll and Sommervoll \(2019\)](#).⁴

Price zones are useful because they provide an empirical ranking of locations by similar estimated location premiums while holding observable dwelling attributes constant. This ranking is central to our analysis of the urban location hierarchy, since it allows us to classify areas into prime, secondary, and distressed submarkets and examine whether quality ripples differ across such locations. However, because the price-zone classification is estimated from transaction prices and uses the same dataset, it may be correlated with unobserved factors that also affect search intensity. We therefore include conventional administrative areas as

⁴The authors gratefully acknowledge Dag Einar Sommervoll for providing the price-zone classification used in this article.

Figure 3: Descriptive Statistics: Search Intensity by Quality Tier in Four Urban Areas

Notes: The figure shows the average search intensity by housing quality tier (low, medium, high). Search intensity is measured as the four-quarter rolling average of buyers registered as interested per listed unit within each quality tier. For Trondheim, the number of bidders is used instead. *DP* denotes four-quarter house price growth in the official local house price index. Source: Eiendomsverdi ASA.

an alternative spatial aggregation.

To identify turning points in the local house price cycle, we apply the [Harding and Pagan \(2002\)](#) procedure, based on the [Bry and Boschan \(1971\)](#) algorithm. In our application, we use relatively “soft” censoring rules, with a minimum phase length of two months and a minimum cycle length of five months.⁵ These thresholds are motivated by the higher frequency and volatility of housing-market dynamics relative to standard business-cycle applications. Alternative threshold configurations could also be justified and would yield somewhat different boom and bust definitions. However, since search intensity, market tightness, bidder competition, and prices are jointly and sequentially determined⁶, the housing-market cycle need not be fully captured by price turning points alone. Instead of testing multiple alternative phase definitions, we complement the boom–bust specification

⁵The calculations are based on the SSBQ Stata module ([Bracke, 2012](#)).

⁶See the discussion in Section 3.

with a flexible spline model that allows the quality gradient in search intensity to vary smoothly over calendar time.

Identified boom and bust episodes are subsequently ranked according to their *magnitude*, *duration*, and *severity*, following [Agnello and Schuknecht \(2011\)](#). All measures are constructed using the official area real house price index.⁷ Magnitude is defined as cumulative real price growth between turning points, while duration is the number of periods between the corresponding peak and trough. Severity combines these two dimensions and is defined for episode i as

$$Severity_i = (\Delta RP_{i,t,t-j} \times D_i) \times 0.5.$$

The resulting classification yields boom and bust episodes that vary in magnitude, duration, and severity. Because the censoring rules are relatively soft, all periods in the sample are classified as either boom or bust phases. The boom/bust indicators are therefore exhaustive, but may also include short-lived or transitional episodes (see [Appendix B](#)).

The sample period coincides with changes in monetary and credit conditions that provide a relevant context for the identified market phases. Following the oil price decline in 2014–2016, the policy rate was reduced and remained low until 2019, while stricter mortgage regulations introduced a maximum loan-to-income constraint in January 2017. These changes are not used as a source of identifying variation, but are relevant for interpreting potential drivers of the identified boom and bust episodes.

5. Empirical Analysis of Search Intensity by Quality Tier

We examine whether search intensity differs systematically across housing quality tiers over the market cycle. All regressions use compositional weights to adjust for phase-specific differences in the observable composition of listed dwellings. The weights are constructed from a propensity-score model using quality class, location, and hedonic attributes, and target the average treatment effect. The Online Appendix reports covariate balance before and after weighting, as well as unweighted estimates.⁸

5.1. Empirical Specification

As a benchmark, we estimate a phase-based interaction model in which the association between housing quality and search intensity is allowed to differ across market phases. The OLS specification is

$$\log(Search_i) = \alpha + \beta_p \log(AskPrice_i) + \mathbf{X}'_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \gamma_q Q_{iq} + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \delta_r D_{ir} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \lambda_{qr} (Q_{iq} \times D_{ir}) + \varepsilon_i. \quad (5.1)$$

Where $Search_i$ denotes the number of buyers registered as interested or bidders for listing i , with $i = 1, \dots, N$. The vector \mathbf{X}_i includes structural, market, and locational controls,

⁷The nominal price index is deflated by the quarterly consumer price index for Norway excluding energy prices (CPI-ATE, source: Statistics Norway).

⁸The weights are estimated using the [Greifer \(2020\)](#) package in R.

including dwelling type, ownership type, dwelling age, time on market, balcony, distance to the CBD (Haversine distance), price zone indicators, real estate agency indicators, and seasonal dummies. The (final) ask prices are annually deflated by the consumer price index to ensure comparability in real terms over time. The set $\mathcal{Q} = \{\text{low, medium, high}\}$ contains the three quality tiers, and Q_{iq} is an indicator for whether listing i belongs to tier q . The set $\mathcal{R} = \{\text{boom, bust}\}$ contains the market phases, and D_{ir} is an indicator for whether listing i is sold in phase r .

The main benchmark specification is a non-hierarchical version of equation (5.1), where $\gamma_q = \delta_r = 0$. In this specification, the omitted category is the initial six-month baseline period at the beginning of the sample period. In the hierarchical specification, the bust phase is omitted as reference category. The parameters of primary interest are the within-phase contrasts across quality tiers, computed as differences between the relevant quality-by-phase coefficients (λ_{qr}). These contrasts measure whether search intensity differs systematically between low-, medium- and high-quality dwellings within the same market phase, after conditioning on asking price, location, dwelling characteristics, market controls, and the reweighted composition of listings.⁹

In the OLS specification, the coefficients are interpreted as log differences in search intensity. Since search intensity is a strictly positive count variable and exhibits overdispersion, the OLS benchmark is complemented by a zero-truncated negative binomial model. The zero truncation reflects that the estimation sample consists of transacted dwellings, which by construction must have attracted at least one registered interested buyer or bidder.

5.2. Results Benchmark Models

Table 2 reports the benchmark quality-by-phase interaction results. Panel A presents the estimated quality-by-phase coefficients, while Panel B reports within-phase contrasts across quality tiers. The third column in each block omits log ask price to assess whether the estimated quality-by-cycle gradients are sensitive to conditioning on the asking price. This specification captures a broader reduced-form association between quality, affordability, and search intensity, whereas the price-controlled specification estimates quality differences conditional on asking price. Inference is based on HC1 heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors in the OLS specification and on the estimated covariance matrix in the zero-truncated negative binomial models. The significance levels in Panel B are obtained from Wald tests of linear hypotheses.

Considering the results for registered interest, the estimates point to a cyclical pattern in the allocation of buyer attention across housing quality tiers. During boom periods, and after accounting for changes in listing composition, search intensity is relatively higher for lower-quality dwellings. Relative to medium-quality dwellings, low-quality dwellings attract substantially more search, on the order of 15–20 percent, while the gap relative to high-quality dwellings is larger, around 25–30 percent. For instance, the estimated low-

⁹The variance inflation factors for the interaction terms $Q_{iq} \times D_{ir}$ are low, indicating no evidence of problematic multicollinearity.

versus-high search differential is 0.244 in the OLS model and 0.221 in the zero-truncated negative binomial model, corresponding to about 28 and 25 percent higher expected search intensity, respectively. At the same time, high-quality dwellings receive less search than medium-quality dwellings.

The bust-period pattern is not a full reversal of all boom-period contrasts. Low-quality dwellings still attract somewhat more search than medium-quality dwellings, but the differential is smaller. The reversal is clearest at the upper end of the distribution, where high-quality dwellings receive less search than medium-quality dwellings during booms, but more search during busts. Omitting the ask price leaves the qualitative pattern largely unchanged. Table 2 also reports the corresponding quality-by-phase results using the number of bidders as the dependent variable. The bidder results show a similar qualitative pattern. However, estimated contrasts are more sensitive to the inclusion of the ask price variable.

5.3. A Flexible Spline Model

The benchmark specification summarizes the housing cycle using discrete boom and bust indicators. To examine whether the quality gradient in search intensity follows a more complex temporal pattern, we estimate an alternative semi-parametric specification in which housing quality is interacted with a spline in calendar time. This lets each quality tier have its own smooth time profile in search intensity without imposing the phase structure directly. The model is defined as follows:

$$Search_i | \mathbf{X}_i \sim \text{NegBin}^+(\mu_i, \theta), \quad (5.2)$$

$$\log(\mu_i) = \tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta}_p \log(AskPrice_i) + \mathbf{X}_i' \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\lambda}_{qk} (Q_{iq} \times B_k(t_i)). \quad (5.3)$$

Where NegBin^+ denotes the zero-truncated negative binomial distribution, $\mu_i = E(Search_i | \mathbf{X}_i)$, and θ is the dispersion parameter. The vector \mathbf{X}_i includes the same controls as in the benchmark specification. As above, $\mathcal{Q} = \{\text{low, medium, high}\}$ contains the three quality tiers, and Q_{iq} is an indicator for whether listing i belongs to tier q . The functions $B_k(t_i)$ are spline basis functions in calendar time, with $K = 5$ in the empirical implementation. The interaction terms $Q_{iq} \times B_k(t_i)$ allow the time profile of search intensity to differ across quality tiers. As before, the omitted category is the initial six-month baseline period at the beginning of the sample period. We interpret the model using predicted percentage contrasts in expected search intensity across quality tiers, evaluated at mean covariate values and using the same compositional weights as in the benchmark model.

Figure 4 suggests that the estimated quality contrasts vary substantially over time. The spline specification uses a cubic B-spline in monthly calendar time and therefore estimates broad smooth time profiles rather than month-to-month turning points. The spline results should be interpreted as evidence of low-frequency variation in the quality gradient, not as an alternative cycle-dating procedure. The estimated profiles are broadly consistent with the phase-based results, but their timing and magnitude do not align mechanically with

Table 2: Search Intensity and Quality-Tier Dispersion: Registered Interest and Bidders

	Registered interest			Bidders		
	OLS	NegBin	NegBin No ask price	OLS	NegBin	NegBin No ask price
<i>Panel A: Core Regression Coefficients</i>						
log(Ask price)	0.101** (0.033)	0.008 (0.020)	–	-0.313*** (0.026)	-0.487*** (0.026)	–
log(Distance CBD)	-0.213*** (0.017)	-0.218*** (0.010)	-0.234*** (0.010)	-0.064*** (0.014)	-0.118*** (0.013)	-0.156*** (0.013)
Low × Boom	0.969*** (0.065)	0.967*** (0.037)	0.946*** (0.042)	0.328*** (0.046)	0.493*** (0.045)	0.586*** (0.051)
Medium × Boom	0.809*** (0.063)	0.802*** (0.035)	0.777*** (0.042)	0.196*** (0.044)	0.327*** (0.044)	0.282*** (0.051)
High × Boom	0.725*** (0.065)	0.746*** (0.036)	0.733*** (0.042)	0.185*** (0.046)	0.326*** (0.045)	0.239*** (0.052)
Low × Bust	0.659*** (0.066)	0.584*** (0.036)	0.549*** (0.044)	0.022 (0.047)	0.068 (0.045)	0.083 (0.054)
Medium × Bust	0.561*** (0.064)	0.497*** (0.035)	0.451*** (0.042)	-0.014 (0.044)	-0.024 (0.044)	-0.159*** (0.053)
High × Bust	0.654*** (0.068)	0.628*** (0.037)	0.585*** (0.044)	0.053 (0.049)	0.094** (0.046)	-0.093* (0.056)
Location factors	x	x	x	x	x	x
Housing/ownership factors	x	x	x	x	x	x
Seasonal dummies	x	x	x	x	x	x
Agency/Marketing factors	x	x	x	x	x	x
Compositional weights	x	x	x	x	x	x
Observations	8,470	8,470	8,470	8,470	8,470	8,470
Adj. R^2 / Log-Lik.	0.181	-60,738.87	-61,584.37	0.094	-30,091.09	-31,033.18
Dispersion parameter θ	–	2.388***	2.298***	–	4.149***	3.820***
<i>Panel B: Search Dispersion (Relative Differences)</i>						
<i>Low vs. Medium</i>						
Boom	0.160***	0.165***	0.169***	0.132***	0.166***	0.304***
Bust	0.098**	0.087***	0.098***	0.037	0.093***	0.242***
<i>Low vs. High</i>						
Boom	0.244***	0.221***	0.213***	0.142***	0.167***	0.347***
Bust	0.005	-0.044*	-0.036	-0.031	-0.025	0.176**
<i>High vs. Medium</i>						
Boom	-0.084**	-0.056**	-0.044**	-0.010	-0.001	-0.043
Bust	0.093*	0.131***	0.134***	0.067*	0.118***	0.066

Notes: HC1 heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors are reported for OLS. Model-based standard errors are reported for the zero-truncated NegBin models. In columns 1–3, the dependent variable is registered interest, logged in the OLS model and in levels in the zero-truncated NegBin models. In columns 4–6, the dependent variable is bidders. The “No ask price” specifications omit log ask price. Panel B reports within-phase linear contrasts across quality tiers, with significance based on Wald tests. Percentage differences can be computed as $100[\exp(\hat{\delta}) - 1]$. The dispersion parameters are reported as $\theta = \exp(\hat{a}_2)$. Significance level: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Figure 4: Spline-Implied Search Dispersion Across Housing Quality Tiers

Notes: The figure shows estimated relative differences in expected search intensity across housing quality tiers over time. Estimates are based on a zero-truncated negative binomial model in which quality-tier indicators are interacted with a cubic B-spline in monthly calendar time with five degrees of freedom. Percentage differences are computed from predicted log contrasts between quality tiers. Green shaded areas indicate price-boom periods and grey shaded areas indicate price-bust periods.

the discrete price-cycle regimes. This suggests that search intensity captures a broader market-tightness margin than contemporaneous price growth alone.

5.4. Other Urban Markets and Intra-City Submarkets

Next, we examine whether similar quality gradients appear in other urban markets and within Oslo submarkets. The additional cities are Trondheim, Drammen, and Tromsø. These markets differ in size and price volatility during the study period. Market phases are defined using the same price-cycle procedure as for Oslo, based on local monthly HPI data. Quality tiers are constructed as before, asking prices are deflated annually using the CPI, and the regressions control for administrative areas rather than price zones due to data constraints.

Figure 5 reports predicted differences in search intensity across quality tiers from hierarchical zero-truncated negative binomial models by city.¹⁰ The Trondheim model uses bidders as the dependent variable, while the remaining models use registered interest. Overall, the results point to a systematic cyclical pattern in the allocation of search inten-

¹⁰Regression results are reported in the Online Appendix.

sity across housing quality tiers in three out of four cities, broadly in line with the Oslo results. These results suggest that the main pattern is not unique to Oslo, although its magnitude varies across urban markets.

Figure 5: Hierarchical-model contrasts in search intensity across quality tiers

Notes: The figure reports estimated contrasts in search intensity across housing quality tiers estimated from hierarchical zero-truncated negative binomial models. Points show percentage differences, computed as $(\exp(\hat{\delta}) - 1) \times 100$. Horizontal lines indicate 95 percent confidence intervals. The vertical dashed line denotes zero. Triangles indicate estimates or confidence intervals truncated at ± 50 percent for readability. Trondheim uses bidders as the dependent variable. The remaining cities use registered interest.

To examine within-city heterogeneity in Oslo, we estimate a hierarchical pooled model in which housing quality, market phase, and price-zone groups are fully interacted. This retains the full Oslo sample while allowing the difference between boom and bust periods in the quality gradient to vary across prime, secondary, and distressed locations.

The Oslo submarket results indicate that the aggregate estimates mask some within-city heterogeneity. In bust periods, the relatively stronger search for high-quality dwellings is concentrated in prime and secondary locations and is weak in distressed locations. This suggests that the quality gradient in search intensity depends partly on location quality. Apart from this difference, the submarket results are broadly consistent with the aggregate Oslo estimates. The empirical model specification and results are given in [Appendix D](#).

6. Robustness Analysis

This section reports robustness checks for the cross-sectional search-intensity results. Across specifications, the broad quality-by-cycle pattern remains similar. We assess sensitivity to omitted valuation information, the parameterization of the quality-by-cycle relationship, the construction of housing-quality tiers, and the definition of spatial fixed effects. Detailed results are reported in the Online Appendix.

First, we use the subsample for which automated valuation model (AVM) estimates are observed at the time of sale ($N = 5,920$). The AVM subsample is broadly similar to the main Oslo sample in terms of search participation, but includes somewhat larger and higher-priced dwellings.¹¹ The AVM is estimated from a richer set of dwelling and neighborhood characteristics than those available in our main dataset and is based on a larger national sample. We construct an AVM-X residual from a first-stage regression of log AVM valuation on the log ask price and the same observed controls as in the search-intensity models.¹² Including this additional valuation-relevant information leaves the main quality-by-cycle pattern essentially unchanged.

Second, we estimate a hierarchical version of the quality-by-phase model with quality main effects, a boom indicator, and quality-by-boom interactions. Because interaction coefficients in this specification are less directly comparable to the baseline contrasts, the model is evaluated using predicted log mean responses at the sample means of the control variables. Some individual contrasts differ modestly in magnitude, but the ordering and economic interpretation of the quality gradients are preserved.¹³

Third, the baseline model is re-estimated using an alternative size-only quality classification. Small dwellings below 50 square meters are classified as low quality, intermediate-size dwellings as medium quality, and spacious dwellings above the upper threshold as high quality. The magnitude of the estimated contrasts changes, but the relative gradients remain broadly similar.

Finally, the main specification is re-estimated using administrative-area fixed effects instead of estimated price zones. The results are highly similar to the baseline estimates, particularly for the quality-by-market-phase contrasts. Taken together, these checks indicate that the main quality-by-cycle pattern is not driven by the spatial aggregation, the quality definition, the model parameterization, or the inclusion of additional valuation-relevant information.

¹¹Mean transaction and asking prices are about five percent higher in the AVM subsample, and average dwelling size is about six percent higher.

¹²The first-stage regression has an adjusted R^2 of 0.959, with a positive and statistically significant coefficient on log ask price.

¹³These Oslo results are reported graphically in Figure 5 along with the other cities, and the exact estimates are given in Appendix D.

7. Supporting Mechanisms and Validation

7.1. The Different Stages of Search

This subsection provides a complementary test of the paper’s staged-search interpretation. Registered interest captures listing-specific attention after buyers have moved beyond initial screening, while bidding reflects active participation in the auction. The theoretical model formalizes this distinction by allowing the transition from registered interest to bidding to depend on asking price. Empirically, the aim is not to estimate a structural price elasticity of search, but to examine whether pricing variables are differently associated with participation at the two observed stages.

To test this directly, Table 3 reports stacked listing-by-stage specifications estimated for the AVM valuation subsample. Each listing enters twice, once with registered interest as the outcome and once with bidders as the outcome. This structure compares the two participation margins within the same set of listings and provides a direct test of whether the pricing association differs across stages. The dependent variable is $\log(1 + y)$, and standard errors are clustered at the listing level.

Table 3: Stacked Stage Comparison of Price Associations

	Registered interest	Bidders	Difference Bidders – interest
<i>Panel A: Ask-price level</i>			
log(Ask price)	-0.391*** (0.065)	-0.533*** (0.042)	-0.142*** (0.049)
<i>Panel B: AVM decomposition</i>			
Overpricing gap	-1.028*** (0.091)	-0.889*** (0.060)	0.139** (0.065)
log(AVM valuation)	0.090 (0.080)	-0.265*** (0.050)	-0.355*** (0.060)
<i>Panel C: Model controls</i>			
Location factors	x	x	x
Housing/ownership factors	x	x	x
Agency factors	x	x	x
Monthly fixed effects	x	x	x
Controls × bidder-stage indicator	x	x	x
Stacked observations	11,840	11,840	11,840
AVM listings	5,920	5,920	5,920

Notes: The table reports linear combinations from stacked listing-by-stage OLS models estimated on the AVM valuation subsample. Each listing enters twice, once with registered interest as the outcome and once with bidders as the outcome. The dependent variable is $\log(1 + y)$. The bidder-stage indicator equals one for bidder observations and zero for registered-interest observations. The column labeled “Difference” reports the interaction between the bidder-stage indicator and the relevant pricing variable. Panel A uses log ask price. Panel B decomposes ask price into log AVM valuation and an overpricing gap, defined as $\log(\text{Ask}) - \log(\text{AVM})$. All specifications include the controls listed in Panel C, interacted with the bidder-stage indicator. Standard errors, in parentheses, are clustered at the listing level. Significance level: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Panel A shows that the asking-price level is more strongly negatively associated with bidding than with registered interest. The coefficient on log ask price is -0.391 for registered interest and -0.533 for bidders. The difference between the two stages is -0.142 and statistically significant. This is consistent with asking price becoming more consequential as buyers move from listing-specific attention to active auction entry.

Panel B decomposes asking price into an AVM-based value component and an overpricing gap, defined as $\log(\text{Ask}) - \log(\text{AVM})$. The overpricing gap is strongly negatively associated with both stages. The implied coefficient is -1.028 for registered interest and -0.889 for bidders. The stage difference is therefore weaker, and in the opposite direction, for the overpricing gap than for the asking-price level. This suggests that pricing relative to underlying value affects listing-specific attention broadly, while the overall asking-price level is more consequential for the transition into bidding. The log AVM valuation component is negatively associated with bidders but not with registered interest, consistent with the bidder stage being more sensitive to the overall price level of the dwelling.

These estimates should be interpreted as conditional associations. Asking prices are chosen by sellers and may reflect both underlying housing value and strategic pricing behavior. The results nevertheless support the interpretation that the two measures capture different points in the matching process. Separate zero-truncated negative binomial specifications, reported in the Online Appendix, yield a similar qualitative interpretation.

7.2. Time Series Analysis and Ripple Effects

This section examines whether the time ordering between search intensity and prices is consistent with the paper’s interpretation of search as an early indicator of market tightness. The analysis is complementary to the listing-level regressions. We use VAR models, Granger-causality tests, and local projections to ask whether registered interest tends to move before prices within and across segments, and whether these dynamics line up with the cross-sectional patterns documented above.

To examine these dynamics, we construct quarterly search series by quality tier and estimate the corresponding quality-specific hedonic house price indexes. These correspond to the quarterly series displayed in Figure 3. The price indexes are estimated using a pooled semi-log hedonic model described in Appendix C. This approach uses the full Oslo sample to estimate common hedonic controls, while permitting separate price-index paths for low-, medium-, and high-quality dwellings. Episode-specific price growth is calculated using the same cycle-dating procedure as above applied to quarterly price indexes.

Table 4 reports estimated price growth by quality tier. During the main boom episode, price growth was strongest for low-quality dwellings. Between 2013Q3 and 2017Q1, low-quality dwellings increased by 56.2 percent, compared with 32.9 percent for medium-quality dwellings and 29.0 percent for high-quality dwellings. The same ranking holds when the boom endpoint is extended by one quarter, although the difference is notably smaller.¹⁴ During the subsequent bust, price declines are more similar across quality tiers, ranging from 10.9 to 13.3 percent. These results suggest that stronger search intensity for lower-quality dwellings during booms is accompanied by stronger price growth in this segment.

In the next section, we examine the joint dynamics of search intensity and prices in a VAR framework to assess their interaction and potential ripple effects more directly.

¹⁴The alternative endpoint accounts for the fact that quality-specific hedonic indexes may peak one quarter earlier or later than the aggregate cycle-dating algorithm, reflecting the fact that medium- and high-quality prices continue to increase between the latter quarter, while the low-quality index is already close to its local peak.

Table 4: Hedonic price growth across quality tiers

<i>Panel A: Cumulative hedonic price growth by quality tier</i>			
Episode	Low	Medium	High
Main boom episode: 2013Q3–2017Q1	56.2	32.9	29.0
Alternative boom endpoint: 2013Q3–2017Q2	57.6	42.5	45.1
Bust episode: 2017Q2–2018Q1	-13.3	-10.9	-12.6
<i>Panel B: Tests of differences in cumulative log growth</i>			
Episode and contrast	Log growth diff.	SE	p-value
<i>Main boom episode: 2013Q3–2017Q1</i>			
Low – Medium	0.162***	(0.051)	0.002
Low – High	0.192***	(0.049)	0.000
High – Medium	-0.030	(0.047)	0.520
<i>Alternative boom endpoint: 2013Q3–2017Q2</i>			
Low – Medium	0.101**	(0.050)	0.045
Low – High	0.083*	(0.048)	0.083
High – Medium	0.018	(0.045)	0.687
<i>Bust episode: 2017Q2–2018Q1</i>			
Low – Medium	-0.027	(0.021)	0.190
Low – High	-0.008	(0.030)	0.800
High – Medium	-0.020	(0.029)	0.496

Notes: Panel A reports cumulative hedonic price growth in percent by quality tier. Panel B reports tests of differences in cumulative log HPI growth across quality tiers. The log growth difference is computed as $\Delta_q - \Delta_{q'}$, where Δ_q is cumulative log HPI growth for quality tier q . Standard errors are heteroskedasticity-robust and computed using the full variance-covariance matrix of the pooled hedonic model. Relative differences can be obtained as $100[\exp(\Delta_q - \Delta_{q'}) - 1]$. Significance level: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

7.3. Search and Price Ripples: VAR Models, Granger Causality, and Local Projections

To examine the dynamic relationship between search intensity and final transaction prices, we estimate bivariate vector autoregressive (VAR) models for different quality and spatial segments. The purpose is twofold. First, we test whether search intensity and prices predict each other within segments. Second, we examine whether changes in search or prices in one segment precede changes in other segments. This provides evidence on potential ripple effects across both price zones and quality tiers. Due to a short time sample length ($N=24$ quarters) and potential issues related to multiple pairwise Granger Causality-tests, we treat the evidence as exploratory.

The VAR framework treats search intensity and prices as jointly related equilibrium outcomes. At the same time, the staged-search setting provides a natural timing rationale for focusing on registered interest, since it is observed before the auction is completed and before the final transaction price is realized. Registered interest is therefore a plausible candidate leading indicator of market pressure.

The bivariate models describe lead-lag relationships and dynamic associations that may indicate propagation across market segments. We complement the Granger-causality tests with local projections (Jordà, 2005), which trace the response of one variable to innovations in another over different horizons. This allows us to investigate the timing, persistence, and direction of the dynamic responses. These relationships are estimated for the total market, within spatial and quality segments, and across segments. The VAR

model is defined as

$$Y_{qm,t} = \beta_{0,qm} + \sum_{\ell=1}^p \beta_{\ell,qm} Y_{qm,t-\ell} + \sum_{\ell=1}^s \gamma_{\ell,qm} X_{qm,t-\ell} + \varepsilon_{qm,t}. \quad (7.1)$$

Where $Y_{qm,t}$ and $X_{qm,t}$ denote the two variables tested for Granger causality in quality segment q and market segment m . Depending on the specification, the variables are registered interest or house price growth, measured for the full market or for specific quality and price-zone segments. To ensure stationarity, all variables are seasonally adjusted and measured as first differences of logarithms. The number of lags is selected using the Schwarz Bayesian information criterion (BIC), with a maximum of four lags due to the relatively short time series.

To test whether X Granger-causes Y , we use a Wald test of

$$H_0 : \gamma_{1,qm} = \gamma_{2,qm} = \dots = \gamma_{s,qm} = 0.$$

Rejection of the null hypothesis implies that lagged values of X contain predictive information for Y , conditional on lagged values of Y .

We estimate local projections as

$$Y_{qm,t+h} = \alpha_{h,qm} + \beta_{h,qm} X_{qm,t} + \sum_{\ell=1}^p \phi_{h\ell,qm} Y_{qm,t-\ell} + \sum_{\ell=1}^s \psi_{h\ell,qm} X_{qm,t-\ell} + \varepsilon_{qm,t+h}. \quad (7.2)$$

The coefficient $\beta_{h,qm}$ traces the response of Y in segment (q, m) at horizon h to an innovation in $X_{qm,t}$, controlling for the same lag structure as in the corresponding VAR.

7.4. Results from VAR Models and Local Projections

We first test for price ripples across price zones, following the classical literature on spatial house price diffusion (e.g., [Clapp and Tirtiroglu, 1994](#); [Pollakowski and Ray, 1997](#)). [Table 5](#) reports Granger-causality tests between house price indexes in prime, secondary, and distressed submarkets. The results provide evidence of price spillovers *down* the location hierarchy, as prices in prime and secondary locations predict prices in distressed locations. At the same time, prices in secondary locations also predict prices in prime locations, indicating more complex dynamics than a simple one-directional ripple from prime to secondary areas.

The dynamic relationship between search intensity and prices within segments is then examined. [Table 6](#) shows that house prices predict search intensity in only a few cases, most clearly for low-quality dwellings in prime locations and for all quality tiers in distressed locations. By contrast, search intensity predicts house prices in a broader set of segments, often with lags of one to two quarters. This pattern is consistent with registered interest containing information about subsequent price movements.¹⁵

¹⁵Simultaneity is detected for low-quality dwellings in prime locations and the market in total in distressed locations.

Table 5: Granger Causality Tests I: Prices Across Zones

From	To	F	p-value	Lags
<i>Upward</i>				
Secondary	Prime	12.854	0.000***	2
Distressed	Prime	2.923	0.077*	4
Distressed	Secondary	0.950	0.408	2
<i>Downward</i>				
Prime	Secondary	0.141	0.869	2
Prime	Distressed	6.502	0.008***	4
Secondary	Distressed	8.731	0.003***	2

Notes: The table reports pairwise Granger-causality tests for HPI series across zones. The VAR lag length is selected by BIC with a maximum of four lags. Significance level: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 6: Granger Causality Tests II: Prices and Search Intensity

		Prices → Search			Search → Prices		
Price zone	Quality	F	p-value	Lag	F	p-value	Lag
Prime	Low	14.673	0.000***	2	8.951	0.002***	2
Secondary	Low	1.269	0.274	1	5.727	0.027**	1
Distressed	Low	1.458	0.262	2	5.772	0.013**	2
City total	Low	3.837	0.065	1	1.537	0.230	1
Prime	Medium	0.109	0.745	1	1.921	0.182	1
Secondary	Medium	0.453	0.509	1	0.973	0.336	1
Distressed	Medium	0.587	0.453	1	8.959	0.008***	1
City total	Medium	1.415	0.249	1	7.569	0.013**	1
Prime	High	0.016	0.899	1	0.286	0.599	1
Secondary	High	0.672	0.524	2	3.182	0.069	2
Distressed	High	0.060	0.809	1	5.241	0.034**	1
City total	High	1.415	0.249	1	0.339	0.567	1
Prime	All	0.176	0.68	1	1.816	0.194	1
Secondary	All	2.194	0.155	1	8.927	0.008***	1
Distressed	All	4.876	0.040**	1	7.569	0.013**	1
City total	All	2.181	0.156	1	14.120	0.001***	1

Notes: The table reports pairwise Granger-causality tests for registered-interest and HPI series series across quality tiers within locations. The VAR lag length is selected by BIC with a maximum of four lags. Significance level: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

The local projection estimates provide broadly similar evidence. Figure 6 shows dynamic linkages in search intensity across quality tiers for the city as a whole. The most visible pattern is downward in the quality hierarchy, where shocks to search in higher- or medium-quality segments are followed by responses in lower-quality segments. This is consistent with the Granger-causality results and with the interpretation that search pressure may propagate across quality tiers.

We also examine the same relationships within location segments. The results, reported in the Online Appendix, suggest similar search ripples across quality segments, although

the timing and strength of the responses vary across prime, secondary, and distressed locations. For instance, high-quality search predicts low-quality search in prime locations, while medium-quality search predicts low-quality search in distressed locations. There is also some evidence of upward dynamics, particularly in prime locations, consistent with the partial reversal of the quality gradient during weaker market phases. Some responses appear to unfold more slowly, especially in distressed locations.

The remaining local projection results provide complementary evidence on price and search dynamics. Price responses across locations are mostly positive, although the timing varies across links. Price-to-search responses are concentrated in fewer segments, while search-to-price responses are more often positive and more widely distributed. Taken together, the dynamic evidence is broadly consistent with the theoretical model and the main cross-sectional results. Registered interest appears to contain early information about market pressure, and this pressure may propagate across both quality and location segments.

Figure 6: Local Projection Estimates for Search Across Quality Tiers for the City Total

Notes: Each panel reports the response of search intensity in one quality tier to a shock (one-percent increase) in search intensity in another quality tier for the city. For instance, “Low on medium” reports the response of search intensity for low-quality dwellings to a one-percent increase in search intensity for medium-quality dwellings. The vertical axis shows the percent response of search intensity. The horizontal axis shows quarters after the shock. Shaded areas indicate confidence intervals.

8. Conclusion

This paper studies housing-market search intensity as a measure of within-city market tightness. Using transaction-level auction data from Norwegian urban housing markets, we observe late-stage participation in specific dwellings through registered interest and bidding. These margins of buyer participation remain largely unobserved in existing housing-market research. The main contribution is to show how late-stage search participation is

distributed across the quality dimension of the housing stock over the housing cycle.

The main finding is that demand pressure is not distributed uniformly across housing quality tiers. During boom periods, lower-quality dwellings attract relatively more search participation. During bust periods, this gradient weakens and partly reverses toward higher-quality dwellings. These patterns persist after reweighting for differences in listing composition and are robust across alternative specifications.

However, these phase-based estimates should be interpreted as average differences across price-cycle regimes. A flexible spline specification yields a similar broad pattern, but shows that the quality gradient in search is not mechanically tied to price-cycle turning points. This is consistent with search intensity capturing a broader market-tightness margin than contemporaneous price growth alone.

The findings add a search-based dimension to the literature on segmented housing markets. Models of filtering, life-cycle mobility, and assignment imply that housing-cycle shocks need not affect all parts of the housing stock symmetrically (Sweeney, 1974a; Ho et al., 2008; Ortalo-Magne and Rady, 2006; Landvoigt et al., 2015; Anenberg and Bayer, 2020). Existing empirical work has mainly documented such heterogeneity through prices, turnover, or inventories. This paper instead shows that buyer participation itself varies systematically across quality tiers.

The results also complement recent work using online search data. Piazzesi et al. (2020) and Gargano et al. (2023) show that search ranges are segmented and can broaden across neighborhoods and housing characteristics when local market conditions change. Our evidence is consistent with this view, but comes from a later stage of the search process. Registered interest and bidding measure participation in particular dwellings close to the transaction stage, allowing search intensity to be interpreted as a dwelling-level indicator of market pressure rather than as a measure of consideration-set breadth.

The mechanisms behind the quality gradients are likely to be multiple. One interpretation, consistent with segmented-search models such as Williams (2018), is that stronger competition in preferred segments lowers the relative return to participation there and generates spillovers towards secondary segments. Other equilibrium channels may reinforce or weaken this mechanism. For instance, Moen et al. (2021) show that seller sequences affect buyer–seller ratios and can amplify housing-market dynamics. In our setting, such mechanisms may operate through changes in market tightness, buyer composition, or listing timing, even though the empirical analysis adjusts for observable changes in listing composition.

The supporting analyses point in the same direction. Asking prices are more strongly negatively associated with bidding than with registered interest, suggesting that price becomes more consequential as participation moves from listing-specific attention to auction entry. In the time-series analysis, quality-specific search is associated with price growth in the expected direction, and changes in registered interest often precede changes in transaction prices. These results support the interpretation of search intensity as an early indicator of market pressure while remaining exploratory.

The findings are likely to be relevant beyond auction-based housing markets, although

the institutional channel may differ. In auction markets, search intensity maps directly into bidder competition. In negotiated-sale markets, similar pressure may operate through multiple offers or bargaining power rather than formal bidding.

Several limitations remain. Most importantly, we do not observe individual buyers across listings or auctions and therefore cannot separate individual search reallocation from changes in buyer composition. Future work linking search histories, financial constraints, and auction participation would make it possible to distinguish these channels more directly and to examine how quality and location propagation interact at the buyer level.

Appendix A. Search Model Derivations

A.1 Interest Probability

Let valuations in segment j follow a Pareto distribution:

$$F_j(v) = 1 - \left(\frac{v}{\bar{v}_j}\right)^{-\alpha_j}, \quad v \geq \bar{v}_j, \quad \alpha_j > 1.$$

A buyer registers interest in a listing if $v_j \geq a_j$, where a_j is the ask price. Hence

$$\iota_j(a_j) = 1 - F_j(a_j) = \left(\frac{a_j}{\bar{v}_j}\right)^{-\alpha_j}, \quad a_j \geq \bar{v}_j.$$

A.2 Expected Surplus Conditional on Winning

Let p_j denote the final transaction price in segment j . Under the Pareto distribution and for $p_j \geq \bar{v}_j$,

$$E[v_j \mid v_j \geq p_j] = \frac{\alpha_j}{\alpha_j - 1} p_j.$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta_j(p_j) = E[v_j - p_j \mid v_j \geq p_j] = \frac{p_j}{\alpha_j - 1}.$$

Thus, $\Delta_j(p_j)$ is the expected surplus conditional on winning the auction at price p_j .

A.3 Expected Return and Buyers' Problem

Let $\pi_j(N_j) \in (0, 1]$ denote the probability of winning conditional on entering the auction, where $\pi'_j(N_j) < 0$. Let $\phi_j(a_j) \in (0, 1]$ denote the conversion from registered interest to bidding, where $\phi'_j(a_j) \leq 0$. The expected marginal gross return from one unit of search participation in segment j is

$$R_j = \iota_j(a_j) \phi_j(a_j) \pi_j(N_j) \Delta_j(p_j).$$

Buyers choose $i_H, i_L \geq 0$ to maximize

$$\max_{i_H, i_L \geq 0} \sum_{j \in \{H, L\}} i_j R_j - \frac{\kappa}{2} (i_H + i_L)^2.$$

Because buyers are atomistic, they take a_j , N_j , and p_j as given when choosing participation intensities. For an interior solution, the first-order conditions are

$$R_j = \kappa(i_H + i_L), \quad j \in \{H, L\},$$

or equivalently

$$\iota_j(a_j) \phi_j(a_j) \pi_j(N_j) \Delta_j(p_j) = \kappa(i_H + i_L).$$

Thus, marginal returns to search participation are equalized across active segments.

A.4 Propagation of Shocks

Using the equilibrium relationships

$$I_j = \frac{B i_j \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j}, \quad N_j = \phi_j(a_j) I_j, \quad p_j = P_j(N_j; \bar{v}_j, \alpha_j, a_j),$$

a buyer-demand shock $B \uparrow$ implies

$$\frac{\partial I_j}{\partial B} = \frac{i_j \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j} > 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial N_j}{\partial B} = \phi_j(a_j) \frac{\partial I_j}{\partial B} > 0,$$

and therefore

$$\frac{\partial p_j}{\partial B} = \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial N_j} \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial B} > 0.$$

The effect on the net return from auction participation can be decomposed as

$$\frac{d}{dB} [\pi_j(N_j) \Delta_j(p_j)] = \pi'_j(N_j) \Delta_j(p_j) \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial B} + \pi_j(N_j) \Delta'_j(p_j) \frac{\partial p_j}{\partial B}.$$

Since $\pi'_j(N_j) < 0$, the first term is negative and captures congestion in the auction stage. The second term is positive and captures the increase in expected surplus conditional on winning. The net effect depends on which force dominates.

A listing-composition shock $S_j \uparrow$ implies

$$\frac{\partial I_j}{\partial S_j} = -\frac{B i_j \iota_j(a_j)}{S_j^2} < 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial N_j}{\partial S_j} = \phi_j(a_j) \frac{\partial I_j}{\partial S_j} < 0,$$

and therefore

$$\frac{\partial p_j}{\partial S_j} = \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial N_j} \frac{\partial N_j}{\partial S_j} < 0.$$

Thus, listing composition affects measured market tightness and final transaction prices even in the absence of a buyer-demand shock.

Appendix B. House Price Cycle-dating Results

Table A1: Boom and Bust Episodes in Real House Prices

<i>Panel A: Boom episodes</i>				
Rank	Episode	Magnitude	Duration	Severity
1	Jul. 2005–Feb. 2007	0.312	20	3.123
2	Nov. 2015–Feb. 2017	0.294	16	2.355
3	Jan. 2014–Jul. 2015	0.210	19	1.996
4	Jan. 2012–Apr. 2013	0.120	16	0.963
5	May 2020–Feb. 2021	0.162	10	0.812
6	Jul. 2003–Feb. 2004	0.187	8	0.747
7	Jan. 2009–Aug. 2009	0.161	8	0.645
8	Aug. 2010–May 2011	0.117	10	0.583
9	Jul. 2004–Feb. 2005	0.104	8	0.414
10	Jan. 2018–Jul. 2018	0.080	7	0.282
11	Jan. 2019–Aug. 2019	0.054	8	0.215
12	Dec. 2021–Aug. 2022	0.045	9	0.202
13	Dec. 2009–May 2010	0.042	6	0.126
14	Jun. 2011–Dec. 2011	0.022	7	0.077
15	Nov. 2019–Feb. 2020	0.033	4	0.066
16	Jul. 2007–Aug. 2007	0.017	2	0.017
17	Jan. 2008–Mar. 2008	0.008	3	0.012
<i>Panel B: Bust episodes</i>				
Rank	Episode	Magnitude	Duration	Severity
1	Mar. 2017–Dec. 2017	-0.138	10	-0.690
2	Apr. 2008–Dec. 2008	-0.147	9	-0.661
3	May 2013–Dec. 2013	-0.088	8	-0.353
4	Mar. 2021–Nov. 2021	-0.047	9	-0.210
5	Sep. 2007–Dec. 2007	-0.066	4	-0.132
6	Sep. 2022–Nov. 2022	-0.079	3	-0.119
7	Aug. 2018–Dec. 2018	-0.036	5	-0.090
8	Aug. 2015–Oct. 2015	-0.038	3	-0.057
9	Mar. 2004–Jun. 2004	-0.028	4	-0.056
10	Mar. 2005–Jun. 2005	-0.047	9	-0.045
11	Mar. 2007–Jun. 2007	-0.018	4	-0.036
12	Sep. 2009–Nov. 2009	-0.024	3	-0.036
13	Mar. 2020–Apr. 2020	-0.035	2	-0.035
14	Sep. 2019–Oct. 2019	-0.024	2	-0.024
15	Jun. 2010–Jul. 2010	-0.013	2	-0.013

Notes: The table reports boom and bust episodes in real house prices identified using the [Harding and Pagan \(2002\)](#) cycle-dating procedure. The sample period for cycle dating is January 2003–April 2023. Magnitude is cumulative real price growth over the episode, duration is measured in months, and severity combines magnitude and duration following [Agnello and Schuknecht \(2011\)](#). Shaded rows indicate episodes that overlap with the transaction sample used in the main analysis.

Appendix C. Hedonic House Price Index Construction and Tests

We estimate a pooled hedonic model defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(P_{igt}) = & \alpha^H + \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{T}} \delta_{\tau}^H D_{\tau t} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \theta_q^H Q_{iq} + \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \lambda_{\tau q}^H (D_{\tau t} \times Q_{iq}) \\ & + \mathbf{Z}'_{it} \boldsymbol{\beta}^H + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \phi_q^H (Q_{iq} \times \ln \text{Size}_i) + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \psi_q^H (Q_{iq} \times \ln \text{Age}_i) + \varepsilon_{igt}^H. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Where P_{igt} is the total transaction price of dwelling i in quality tier q sold in quarter t . The set $\mathcal{Q} = \{\text{low, medium, high}\}$ contains the three quality tiers, and Q_{iq} is an indicator for whether dwelling i belongs to tier q . The set \mathcal{T} contains the quarterly time periods, and $D_{\tau t}$ is an indicator for whether transaction quarter t equals quarter τ . Reference categories are omitted where required to avoid collinearity. The vector \mathbf{Z}_{it} contains the remaining dwelling and location controls, excluding size and age, including house type, ownership type, price-zone fixed effects, balcony, and distance to the CBD. The terms $Q_{iq} \times \ln \text{Size}_i$ and $Q_{iq} \times \ln \text{Age}_i$ allow the effects of size and dwelling age to vary across quality tiers.

The quality-specific hedonic house price index is obtained from predicted log prices from equation (A1). For each quality tier q , the index in quarter t is computed as

$$\text{HPI}_{qt} = 100 \times \exp \left(\widehat{\ln P}_{qt} - \widehat{\ln P}_{q0} \right),$$

where $\widehat{\ln P}_{qt}$ is the predicted log price for quality tier q in quarter t , evaluated at fixed covariate values, and quarter 0 is the base period. Episode-specific hedonic price growth for quality tier q between quarters t_0 and t_1 is then calculated as

$$\text{Growth}_{q,t_0,t_1} = 100 \times \left[\exp \left(\widehat{\ln P}_{qt_1} - \widehat{\ln P}_{qt_0} \right) - 1 \right].$$

To assess whether quality-specific hedonic price growth differs statistically across housing quality tiers, we test linear combinations of the estimated quality-specific time effects from the pooled hedonic model. For each episode, we calculate the difference in log HPI growth between two quality tiers, for instance $(\Delta \log \text{HPI}_{\text{Low}}) - (\Delta \log \text{HPI}_{\text{Medium}})$, where $\Delta \log \text{HPI}$ is measured between the start and end quarters of the episode. Standard errors are computed using the full heteroskedasticity-robust variance-covariance matrix of the hedonic model. Table 4 reports the estimates and test results.

Appendix D. Other Urban Markets and Oslo Submarkets: Model Specification and Results

The Oslo submarket model extends the benchmark specification by allowing the quality-by-phase relationship to differ across the urban location hierarchy. The model is defined as follows:

$$Search_i | \mathbf{X}_i \sim \text{NegBin}^+(\mu_i, \theta), \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\mu_i) = & \tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta}_p \log(AskPrice_i) + \mathbf{X}_i' \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \tilde{\gamma}_q Q_{iq} + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \tilde{\delta}_r D_{ir} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \tilde{\eta}_g G_{ig} \\ & + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \tilde{\lambda}_{qr} (Q_{iq} \times D_{ir}) + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \tilde{\omega}_{qg} (Q_{iq} \times G_{ig}) \\ & + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \tilde{\kappa}_{rg} (D_{ir} \times G_{ig}) + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \tilde{\pi}_{qrg} (Q_{iq} \times D_{ir} \times G_{ig}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

Where $Search_i$ denotes the number of buyers registered as interested for listing i , with $i = 1, \dots, N$. The vector \mathbf{X}_i includes the same structural, market, and locational controls as in the benchmark specification, except that the submarket specification uses price-zone group indicators rather than the full set of price-zone indicators. As above, $\mathcal{Q} = \{\text{low, medium, high}\}$ contains the three quality tiers, and Q_{iq} is an indicator for whether listing i belongs to tier q . The set $\mathcal{R} = \{\text{boom, bust}\}$ contains the market phases, and D_{ir} is an indicator for whether listing i is sold in phase r . The set $\mathcal{G} = \{\text{prime, secondary, distressed}\}$ contains the submarket groups, and G_{ig} is an indicator for whether listing i belongs to group g .

Prime consist of the four highest-ranked price zones, distressed of the four lowest-ranked zones, and secondary consists of the remaining zones. The model includes main effects for quality tier, market phase, and submarket group, as well as all two-way and three-way interactions among these variables. It uses the same compositional weights as the benchmark specification. The submarket model uses common city-wide boom and bust indicators, so the results describe how quality gradients vary across locations under the aggregate Oslo price cycle rather than submarket-specific cycle dynamics. The results are reported in Table A2.

Table A2: Search Intensity and Quality-Tier Dispersion: Other Urban Markets and Submarkets

	Oslo	Oslo submarkets			Trondheim	Drammen	Tromsø
		Prime	Secondary	Distressed			
<i>Relative Differences</i>							
<i>Low vs. Medium</i>							
Boom	0.178***	0.149***	0.204***	0.182***	0.140***	0.150***	-0.398***
Bust	0.103***	0.135***	0.087***	0.180***	0.127***	0.116**	-0.858**
<i>Low vs. High</i>							
Boom	0.214***	0.239***	0.177***	0.267***	0.230***	0.205***	-0.210
Bust	-0.011	0.024	-0.049	0.158**	0.099**	0.185***	-1.270***
<i>High vs. Medium</i>							
Boom	-0.036	-0.089***	0.027	-0.084**	-0.090**	-0.056	-0.188*
Bust	0.114***	0.111**	0.136***	0.022	0.028	-0.069	0.415**
<i>Percentage Differences</i>							
<i>Low vs. Medium</i>							
Boom	19.5	16.1	22.7	20.0	15.0	16.1	-32.8
Bust	10.8	14.4	9.1	19.7	13.6	12.3	-57.6
<i>Low vs. High</i>							
Boom	23.8	27.0	19.4	30.6	25.8	22.8	-18.9
Bust	-1.1	2.4	-4.8	17.2	10.4	20.4	-72.0
<i>High vs. Medium</i>							
Boom	-3.5	-8.6	2.7	-8.1	-8.6	-5.4	-17.1
Bust	12.1	11.7	14.6	2.2	2.9	-6.7	51.5

Notes: Entries in the upper panel report log differences in predicted search intensity across quality tiers from hierarchical zero-truncated negative binomial models. Entries in the lower panel report percentage differences, computed as $(\exp(\hat{\delta}) - 1) \times 100$. The aggregate Oslo column is estimated from the city-level hierarchical model. The Oslo submarket columns are derived from a pooled Oslo model in which housing quality, market phase, and submarket group are fully interacted. Submarkets are defined from price-zone rankings as prime, secondary, and distressed locations. The boom and bust indicators are defined at the city level. The Trondheim model uses the number of bidders as the dependent variable. The remaining models use registered interest. Statistical significance is based on Wald tests of linear contrasts using the estimated variance-covariance matrix. Significance level: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

Appendix E. Supplementary Literature Table

Table A3: Related Literature on Housing Segmentation and Market Outcomes

Research	Approach	Quality definition	Shock	Outcomes
Sweeney (1974a)	Filtering model with quality segments and heterogeneous households. Theoretical model	Quality hierarchies defined generally	Income	Demand, prices
Piazzesi, Schneider, and Stroebel (2020)	Search model with segmented search and heterogeneous buyers, using listing-screening data. Theoretical and quantified model	Location, price, and size	Moving shocks	Search intensity, inventory, turnover, prices
Williams (2018)	Endogenous search model with quality segments. Theoretical	Location, price, size, and other dimensions ^a	Booms and busts in search intensity and prices	Search intensity, prices, rents
Gargano, Giacoletti, and Jarnecic (2023)	Reduced-form empirical analysis complemented by a quantitative search-and-matching model	Location, housing type, and number of bedrooms	Local house price growth	Search breadth across geography and housing characteristics
Ho et al. (2008)	Dynamic stock-flow model with quality segments and heterogeneous households. Granger causality tests. Theoretical model with empirical support	Size	Wealth	Demand, prices, transaction volumes
Ortalo-Magne and Rady (2006)	Life-cycle model with quality segments and heterogeneous households. Theoretical model with empirical support	"Starter-homes" and "trade-up" homes	Wealth	Demand, prices, transaction volumes
Landvoigt, Piazzesi, and Schneider (2015)	Assignment model with quality segments and heterogeneous buyers. Theoretical and quantified model	Price	Credit	Demand, prices, transaction volumes
Liu et al. (2014)	Optimization model with quality segments. Repeat sales methods. Theoretical and empirical support	Size	Booms and busts in prices	Prices, turnover, supply

Notes: The table summarizes studies that analyze cross-sectional differences in housing-market outcomes across housing segments. It reports the model or empirical approach, the segmentation dimension used to define housing quality or submarkets, the source of shocks, and the main outcome variables. ^aIn Williams (2018), segments may differ along location, price, size, or other dimensions.

References

- Luca Agnello and Ludger Schuknecht. Booms and busts in housing markets: Determinants and implications. *Journal of Housing Economics*, 20(3):171–190, 2011.
- Elliot Anenberg and Patrick Bayer. Endogenous sources of volatility in housing markets: The joint buyer–seller problem. *International Economic Review*, 61(3):1195–1228, 2020.
- Cristian Badarinza, Vimal Balasubramaniam, and Tarun Ramadorai. In search of the matching function in the housing market. *Available at SSRN 4594519*, 2024.
- Alexander N Bogin, William M Doerner, and William D Larson. Local house price paths: accelerations, declines, and recoveries. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 58(2):201–222, 2019.
- Philippe Bracke. Sbbq: Stata module to implement the harding and pagan (2002) business cycle dating algorithm. 2012.
- Gerhard Bry and Charlotte Boschan. Programmed selection of cyclical turning points. In *Cyclical analysis of time series: Selected procedures and computer programs*, pages 7–63. NBER, 1971.
- Paul E Carrillo. An empirical stationary equilibrium search model of the housing market. *International Economic Review*, 53(1):203–234, 2012.

- John M Clapp and Dogan Tirtiroglu. Positive feedback trading and diffusion of asset price changes: Evidence from housing transactions. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 24(3):337–355, 1994.
- John Cubbin. Price, quality, and selling time in the housing market. *Applied Economics*, 6(3):171–187, 1974.
- Antonio Gargano, Marco Giacoletti, and Elvis Jarnecic. Local experiences, search, and spillovers in the housing market. *The Journal of Finance*, 78(2):1015–1053, 2023.
- Noah Greifer. A guide to using weightit for estimating balancing weights, 2020.
- Rangan Gupta and Stephen M Miller. The time-series properties of house prices: A case study of the southern california market. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 44:339–361, 2012.
- Lu Han and William C Strange. The microstructure of housing markets: Search, bargaining, and brokerage. *Handbook of regional and urban economics*, 5:813–886, 2015.
- Lu Han and William C Strange. What is the role of the asking price for a house? *Journal of Urban Economics*, 93:115–130, 2016.
- Don Harding and Adrian Pagan. Dissecting the cycle: a methodological investigation. *Journal of monetary economics*, 49(2):365–381, 2002.
- John P Harding, John R Knight, and Clemon F Sirmans. Estimating bargaining effects in hedonic models: Evidence from the housing market. *Real estate economics*, 31(4):601–622, 2003.
- Darren K Hayunga and Henry J Munneke. Examining both sides of the transaction: Bargaining in the housing market. *Real Estate Economics*, 49(2):663–691, 2021.
- Lok Sang Ho, Yue Ma, and Donald R Haurin. Domino effects within a housing market: The transmission of house price changes across quality tiers. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 37: 299–316, 2008.
- Òscar Jordà. Estimation and inference of impulse responses by local projections. *American economic review*, 95(1):161–182, 2005.
- Paul Klemperer. Auction theory: A guide to the literature. *Journal of economic surveys*, 13(3):227–286, 1999.
- John Krainer. A theory of liquidity in residential real estate markets. *Journal of urban Economics*, 49(1): 32–53, 2001.
- Tim Landvoigt, Monika Piazzesi, and Martin Schneider. The housing market (s) of san diego. *American Economic Review*, 105(4):1371–1407, 2015.
- Chris Leishman. House building and product differentiation: An hedonic price approach. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 16:131–152, 2001.
- Mari O Mamre and Dag Einar Sommervoll. Coming of age: Renovation premiums in housing markets. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, pages 1–36, 2022.
- Geoffrey Meen. Regional house prices and the ripple effect: a new interpretation. *Housing studies*, 14(6): 733–753, 1999.
- Paul R. Milgrom and Robert J. Weber. A theory of auctions and competitive bidding. *Econometrica*, 50 (5):1089–1122, 1982.
- Espen R Moen, Plamen T Nenov, and Florian Sniekers. Buying first or selling first in housing markets. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 19(1):38–81, 2021.
- L Rachel Ngai and Silvana Tenreyro. Hot and cold seasons in the housing market. *American Economic Review*, 104(12):3991–4026, 2014.
- Francois Ortalo-Magne and Sven Rady. Housing market dynamics: On the contribution of income shocks and credit constraints. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 73(2):459–485, 2006.
- Monika Piazzesi and Martin Schneider. Momentum traders in the housing market: Survey evidence and a search model. *American Economic Review*, 99(2):406–11, 2009.
- Monika Piazzesi, Martin Schneider, and Johannes Stroebel. Segmented housing search. *American Economic Review*, 110(3):720–59, 2020.
- Henry O Pollakowski and Traci S Ray. Housing price diffusion patterns at different aggregation levels: an examination of housing market efficiency. *Journal of Housing Research*, pages 107–124, 1997.
- Åvald Sommervoll and Dag Einar Sommervoll. Learning from man or machine: Spatial fixed effects in

- urban econometrics. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 77:239–252, 2019.
- James L Sweeney. A commodity hierarchy model of the rental housing market. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 1(3):288–323, 1974a.
- James L Sweeney. Quality, commodity hierarchies, and housing markets. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, pages 147–167, 1974b.
- William C Wheaton. Vacancy, search, and prices in a housing market matching model. *Journal of political Economy*, 98(6):1270–1292, 1990.
- Joseph Williams. Housing markets with endogenous search: Theory and implications. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 105:107–120, 2018.
- Enwei Zhu, Jing Wu, Hongyu Liu, and Xindian Li. Within-city spatial distribution, heterogeneity and diffusion of house price: Evidence from a spatiotemporal index for beijing. *Real Estate Economics*, 50(3):621–655, 2022.